

A Study on Measures to Overcome the Impact of Stress in IT Employees Work Performance of Bangalore Region

Prof P.Nagaraja Rao^[a]

Mrs. Sandhya Suswaram^[b]

Abstract

Stress is one of the most talked about and most misunderstood topics in the psychological to a stressor. A stressor is any event that requires an action of the individual. Thus stress is not always detrimental phenomenon in fact some stress may facilitate performance. The relationship between the performance and stress is compared to tuning a violin. If there is not enough tension on the strings, there will be no music but if there is too much tension, the strings will break the optimum level of tension will result in maximum performance.

Keywords: Job performance, I T Sector, Stress, Training, Work performance.

^[a]Prof P.Nagaraja Rao

Research Scholar, Bharathiyar University,
Professor, Dept. of Management Studies,
Sir M. V. Institute of Technology, Bengaluru,
Karnataka, India.

Email: nagarajarao_1946@rediffmail.com

Mobile:+91 9739690301

^[b]Mrs. Sandhya Suswaram

Research Scholar, Anna University,
Asst.Professor, Dept. of Management Studies,
Sir M. V. Institute of Technology, Bengaluru,
Karnataka, India.

Email: sandhyavandana@rediffmail.com

Mobile: +91 9986989639

Acme Intellects

1. INTRODUCTION

Stress cannot be avoided but it can be reduced by alternative methods in the working environment. Any problem becomes stress in day to day life. The common factors causing for stress are unhappy, illness, frustration, too much responsibility and they in turn lead to poor productivity, poor morale and lack of interest in the job etc., Management of stress at work is very important if employers wish to make use the most of people potential. Understanding that stress management is an integral part and parcel of management practice, the problem and difficulty words to be avoided instead saying with challenge and opportunity. Physical and mental preparations are very important in the management of stressors. Emotional support, appraisal report, social support, social ties and smooth relationship with others are regarded as emotionally satisfying aspects of life. Ancillary skills of stress management, training relaxation training is some of the management techniques of stress.

This word stringer derived from the Latin word. Stress was commonly used in the 13th century to mean hardship strain, adversity. Pepper (1995) explains that in the workplace or at home emotion constantly being challenged. Tension co-exists in a superior and subordinate position and conversation of confidential or personal matters may trigger emotions at work. Areas of conflict exist in the organization itself, the department, Boss, Sub-cultural group or individual friends. Emotion on betrayal dedication anger disappointment hate or jealousy can be provoked. Stress can also be a common factor in the workforce. This is increasing in the modern life. The result of stress can lead the any extent in the human life. Common stressors are dealing with the workload, problems such as having too much work, staff shortage and company downsizing. Alternatively the problem could be qualitative; the work is too demanding, unsuitable appointment. Insufficient training old equipment or poor instructions. Under stress the employee behavior gets affected both at the workplace and home, examples – could include marriage problems illness and pregnancy, shifting house death or more if not health gets deteriorated.

Stress symptoms can affect the organization by employees loosing commitment, job satisfaction and becoming disenchanted with the profession. Eventually the employee may just decide to leave and it is in the best interest of the company to ensure the workplace is not stressful and to monitor working conditions which may lead to employees becoming stressed out. Cheney (1995) believes that a modern workplace environment today considers the survival of an organization to rely on the organizations efficiency in managing organizational objectives. It is expected that employees have the ability to evaluate and possibly make amendments to the organization's policy and performance to accomplish goals.

Stress as “one of the most inaccurate words in the scientific literature” because it is used to describe “both the sources and the effects of stress process”. Whether stress was a ‘characteristic of the environment an experience felt by the person or a transactional phenomenon created by the process of person interacting with the environment’.

‘Stress’ might be replaced with the more precise term strain in his memory. Stress arises when individuals perceive that they cannot adequately cope with the demands being made on them or with threats to their well being when coping is important to them. Occupational stress is the sum total of factors experienced in relation to work which affect the psychosocial and physiological homeostasis of the worker. The individual factor is termed as a stressor and stress are the individual worker to stressors

1.1 Consequences of stress.

- 1. Physiological consequence:** - Stress takes its toll on the human body. People experience tension, headaches, High B.P high level of cholesterol, ulcer arthritis etc., due to stress. Studies have found that up to 92 percent of patients complain of stress related symptoms and disorders. As per medical researchers wherever people are stressed their blood pressure goes up and down. Frequent pressure change causes injury to the blood vessel walls which makes them constrict and behave abnormally.
- 2. Psychological consequences:-**It may lead to job dissatisfaction; moodiness, depression, anger, anxiety nervousness and tension are the manifestation of the psychological consequences of stress. Emotional fatigue is another psychological consequence of stress.
- 3. Behavioral consequences:** - related to physiological and psychological effects are possible changes in how well employees can perform their jobs. When stress becomes distress, it adversely affects the employee’s behavior. The consequences of high level of stress are underrating or overeating, sleeplessness obesity, increased drinking and smoking. Overstressed also tend higher levels of absenteeism. There may be two reasons for it .One reason is that stress makes people sick. The other reason is that absenteeism is a coping mechanism. Absenteeism is a temporarily withdrawing from the stressful situation so that the successful employee has an opportunity to re-energize.
- 4. Organizational consequences-** usually when employees experience serious problems the organization also suffers. Companies whose employees consistently experience too much stress are likely to experience high levels of absenteeism and turnover. The accident rate may also tend to raise

finally employee satisfaction with the job and with the organization, industrial relations, and productivity can suffer from excessive stress.

Fento (2006) claims there are 10 distinct qualities about American, European, African, and Latin American people that aid the success of a democratic company. They're post-modern strategies include being genuine, open and transparent with employees above issues regarding health strategy and organization's agenda. There is also a commitment to continuous communication and collaboration between employees. Fairness and equality are important in democratic companies and there are no ranking systems. Every employee believes in their company's existence and goals where they strive for the same target.

Stress is the kind of pressure people feel in life. The excessive stress symptoms that harass the employee job performance and health and makes man to be incapable to cope with the environment.

1.2 Sources of stress- Environment sources have an impact on employee stress. The environmental factors to which an employee responds mainly include things like technological changes, family changes and obligation economical and financial conditions race, caste, class. Organizational sources such as organizational policies, procedure structure. Organizational changes are stressful. Examples downsizing is extremely stressful to employees who are losing jobs and who remain in the organization.

Ex. Employees suffering from high B.P doubled after the company laid off 10 percent of its workforce. The reasons being the fear of layoff and overburden work. Recently in one of the MNC's CEO died due to stress. Group also causes stress due lack of group cohesiveness, lack of social support ,interpersonal and intergroup conflict.

Individual causes- Role conflict, Role ambiguity, workload, life events, and personal traits. Stress can be reduced by adopting self management techniques like good nutritional habits-balanced diet and good exercise habits and self awareness, regular relaxation habits-meditation prayer. Effective time management day to day and life and career planning for the long-term.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE.

Stress is an unwanted reaction people have to severe pressures or other types of demands placed upon them. A huge and multi fields literature points a lot of key factors such as work environment, management support, work load etc in determining the stressful the work can be and its effect on employee physical and mental health. According to (Anderson, 2002)^[1] work to family conflicts is also a predecessor which creates stress in employees of an organization. Job stress has also been viewed as dysfunctional for organizations and their members (Kahn, Wolfe, Quinn, Snoek, & Rosenthal, 1964)^[2]. Although stress has been variously viewed as an environmental stimulus to an individual defined stress as an individual's reaction to an environmental force that effect an individual performance. Job related stress can be mostly immobilizing because of its possible threats to family functioning and individual performance.

Job related stress can create a difference between the demands on families and the ability of families to provide material security for them (McCubbin & Figley, 1983)^[3]. While there is a significant body of research which deals with work and family there is relatively little research which deals specifically with perceived job insecurity (i.e., concerns or fears about job loss) and marriage and family life. Stress condition which happens when one realizes the pressures on them, or the requirements of a situation, are wider than their recognition that they can handle, if these requirements are huge and continue for a longer period of time without any interval, mental, physical or behavior problems may occur.

Stress exists in every organization either big or small the workplaces and organizations have become so much complex due to which it exists, workplace stress has significant effects over the employee's job performance, and the organizations are trying to cope with this scenario. Eleven forces are used as an antecedents of stress by researches (Overload, Role vagueness, Role conflict, Responsibility for people, Participation, Lack of feedback, Keeping up with quick technological change, Being in an innovative role, Career growth, Organizational structure and environment, and Recent episodic events.,) Overload :excessive work or work that is outside one's capability (Franch and Caplan ,1972^[4]; Margolis et al, 1974 ; Russek and Zohman, 1958) Role Ambiguity : Role insufficient information concerning powers, authority and duties to perform one's role, Role Conflict: Supervisors or subordinates place contradictory demands on the individual(Beehr et al, 1976; Caplan and Jones, 1975; Caplan, et al, 1975; Hall and Gordon, 1973; Kahn et al, 1964) Responsibility for people: Responsibility for people, well-being works, job security, and professional development (French and Caplan, 1972; Pincherle, 1972) Participation: Extent to which one has influence over decisions relevant to one's job (Kasl, 1973)

Margolis et al, 1974). Lack of Feedback: Lack of information about job performance (Adams, 1980 Cassel, 1974) keeping up with rapid technological change: Keeping up with rapid changes in the information processing field (Ginzburg, 1967) Being in an innovative role: Having to bring about change in the organization (Kahn, et al.1964) Lawrence and Lorsch 1970 ^[5]. Career development: Impact of status dissimilarity, lack of job security, let down ambition (Brook 1973) Erikson and Gunderson 1972; Kahn, et al. 1964) Recent episodic events: Certain life events, such as divorce and bereavement, that are highly stressful (Adams 1980 ; Cobb, 1977 Holmes and Rahe 1975).

(Rose, 2003)^[6] In every organization and at every level of management and workers an elevated average level of stress is to be found which mostly has an effect on employee job satisfaction. According to (Rose , 2003) employees have a tendency towards higher levels of stress regarding time, working for longer hours which reduces employees urge for performing better. Management support helps in reducing or increases stress in employees, (Stamper & Johlke, 2003) apparent organizational assistance, management support work as a cushion which acts positively in decreasing work related stress in employees. There are a lot of reasons causing stress to work family conflicts work overload one of reason identified by (Stamper & Johlke , 2003) that if the organization or management does not appreciate its employees for their hard work or contribution toward the organization creates stress and mostly creates intention to leave.

(Ivancevich & Donnelly, 1975)^[7] studied the link between anxiety stress with satisfaction and performance of employees, that lower anxiety stress improves performance of the employee's which he studied in different managerial level of an organization. (Beehr, Jex, Stacy & Murray, 2000) ^[8] Found the relationship between occupational stressors an performance of employees of an organization as well as it can affect the employees psychologically. (Jamal, 1984) ^[9] Studied an association between job stress and job performance between managers and blue-collar employees. Stress on the job can be stated as the outcome of an individual due to the working environment from which he feels unsecured. Different relationships are projected between job stress and performance: U-shaped and curvilinear, positive linear, negative linear and no relationship between the stress and performance. Variables used for this study were job stress, job performance, and organizational commitment. Very limited evidence is seen for curvilinear or no association.

2.2 Stress Management in organization.

Cramwell-Ward (1995) found only 10% of U.K. Companies had a program to deal with stress although 90% considered that the mental health of their employees was vital to their competitive position.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To overcome the Impact of Stress in IT Employees Work Performance of Bangalore Region.
- To find the stress causes in the work environment and to understand the type of training the IT organization has provided to their employees.
- To identify the major stress causes and methods to manage stress effectively.
- To know-how best alternative methods can be used to overcome stress.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.

Descriptive research studies describe the characteristics of individual groups or situation.

The research design used in this study is descriptive research.

4.1 Population of Study: Bangalore city. A total of 200 employees are taken for this research study.

4.2 Primary Data:

4.2.1 Tools Used: Questionnaire & Interview method.

4.2.2 Sample frame: All employees who are residing in Bangalore.

4.2.3 Sample size: 250

4.3 Secondary Data: Secondary data was carried out using finding of prior studies, published articles papers in journals.

Acme Intellects

5. DATA ANALYSIS.

Table-1: Employees stress level on Monday morning.

Sl.No.	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1	Fully stressed	15	7.5%
2	Moderately stressed	113	56.5%
3	Not stressed	34	17%
4	Cool	38	19%
Total		200	100%

Chart 1: Employees stress level on Monday morning.

Inference: - Most of the respondents nearly 64% feel that they are stressed on Monday morning due to their busy schedules for week targets and pending issues.

Table II: IT Professionals Attendance for stress management training programme.

Sl.No.	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1	Attended	150	75%
2	Not Attended	50	25%
Total		200	100%

Chart 2: IT professional's attendance for stress management Training Programme

Inference: It is seen from the table that stress management programme is not made compulsory.

Acme Intellects

Table III: Confidence level gained after attending stress management training programme.

Sl. No.	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1	Fully Confident	38	19%
2	Confident	86	43%
3	Not Confident	20	10%
4	Not Sure	56	28%
Total		200	100%

Chart 3: Confidence level gained after attending stress management training programme.

Acme Intellects

Table IV: Feedback on training program in reducing stress.

Sl. No.	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1	Very Effective	10	5%
2	Effective	50	25%
3	Not Sure	74	37%
4	Not Related	66	33%
Total		200	100%

Chart 4: Feedback on training program in reducing stress.

Acme Intellects

Table V: Is the stress management programme training necessary or not.

Sl. No.	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1	Very Much Essential	68	34%
2	Good to Have	110	55%
3	Not Sure	12	6%
4	Not Needed	10	5%
Total		200	100%

Chart 5: Is the stress management programme training necessary or not.

Inference: 34% respondents feel it is very much essential and 55% feel stress management training is good to have.

Table-VI: Types of training program are adopted to reduce stress.

Sl. No.	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1	Work Shop	122	61%
2	Seminars	26	13%
3	Guiding	18	9%
4	Consulting	34	17%
Total		200	100%

Chart 6: Types of training program are adopted to reduce stress.

Inference: companies are adopting many training programs for reducing the stress out of which workshops are the best method adopted for reducing the stress.

Table-VII: Types of Physical Activities adopted to reduce stress

Sl. No.	Options	Frequency	Percentage
1	Meditation	50	25%
2	Yoga	30	15%
3	Sports	100	50%
4	Recreation	20	10%
Total		200	100%

Chart 7: Types of Physical Activities adopted to reduce stress

Inference: majority of the employees are said that the sports activity is playing a major role on reducing of the stress at workplace.

Acme Intellects

6. Suggestions and conclusions.

Every human being get stressed by one way or another in the course of his daily life may be due to his work environment or domestic problems. Totally the effect is in physical and mental and social health. Stress among the workforce is concerned it can easily lead to alienation, apathy absenteeism and ultimately interfere with workforce environment. Various types of stressors in the routine life of a workforce make life stressful. Due to this the work performance goes down and thereby reduced production. Finally the worker decides to quit the employer and to change the organization.

The organization should strive hard in the direction of elimination of unwanted stress at workplace. Management should support the worker in giving clear instructions on the work with good planning. Guidance at all the stages which helps the worker feels relieved from stress symptoms. By giving proper guidance and instructions and support the worker feels happy to work without any stress environment. Every one needs to identify the major stressor and also work on the alternatives to overcome stress. Each worker should be aware of the techniques or methods to handle stress. With this planned training programs stress can be managed effectively. Reduction in job stresses leads to higher job satisfaction and thus increases individual growth and organizational productivity.

7. References

- [1]. Anderson E.S., Coffey S.B., & Byerly T.R. (2002). Formal Organizational Initiatives and Informal Workplace Practices: Links to Work-Family Conflict and Job-Related Outcomes. *Journal of Management* 28,787.
- [2]. Kahn, R. L., Wolfe, D. M., Quinn, R. P., Snoek, J. D., & Rosenthal, R. A. (1964). *Organizational stress: Studies in role conflict and ambiguity*. New York: Wiley.
- [3]. McCubbin, H. I., & Figley, C. R. (Eds.). (1983). *Coping with normative transitions (Vol. 1)*. New York: Brunner/Mazel.
- [4]. French, J.R.P., Jr., and Caplan, R.D. (1972). *Organizational Stress and Individual Strain*. in A.J. Marrow, ed., *The Failure of Success*, AMACOM, New York, New York,
- [5]. Lawrence, P., & Lorsch, J. (1967). *Organization and Environment: Managing Differentiation and Integration*. Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts .
- [6]. Rose M. (2003). Good Deal, Bad Deal? Job Satisfaction in Occupations. *Work Employment Society*, 17; 503.
- [7]. Ivancevich M.J. & Donnelly H. J. (1975). Relation of Organizational Structure to Job Satisfaction, Anxiety-Stress, and Performance. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 20, No. 2 , pp. 272-280.

- [8]. Beehr A. T, Jex M.S., Stacy A. B., & Murray A.M. (2000). Work Stressors and Coworker Support as Predictors of Individual Strain and Job Performance. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 21, No. 4, pp. 391-405.
- [9]. Jamal M. (1984). Job Stress and job Performance controversy: an empirical assessment in two countries. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 33:1–21
- [10]. S.S.Khanka(2000) Stress Management. S.Chand&Co.
- [11]. Gopal Krishna R.V. (2005) Aiming for world class Indian Mgt.
- [12]. Hersey parlet –Mgt. Of organization behaviour prentice hall India New Delhi
- [13]. Mallikarjunan.k- Best HRM Practices HRM Review vol.2
- [14]. Aiken(1995)-in cranwell-ward and Aiken “when the going gets tough people management”.
- [15]. CarterF.A. and corlett n(1981)-shiftwork and accidents.
- [16]. Corper C.L and Marshall j (1976) ‘Occupational sources of stress ‘
- [17]. Fletcher .B.C (1988) “The epidemiology of occupational stress”
- [18]. Fench.J.R Caplan R.D and van Harison(1982)- The mechanism of job stress and strain.

Acme Intellects